

A Model for Job requirements and job resources Affecting Employees' Job Engagement

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to provide a model of job requirements and job resources affecting employees' job engagement. The research is of mixed exploratory (qualitative and quantitative) type. To collect qualitative data, themes analysis method and semi-structured interview (with 17 experts using purposive sampling method) and to collect quantitative data, two researcher-made questionnaires, titled (the importance of items and the current situation questionnaire) and the standard Utrecht questionnaire, were also used. The statistical population includes all 200 employees of the Organization of Cinema and Audiovisual Affairs in Iran. In the quantitative section, 127 people were randomly selected as a sample using Morgan's sampling table. The validity of the questionnaires was measured through face validity and confirmatory factor analysis, and the reliability of the questionnaires through Cronbach's alpha was obtained at 0.768, 0.930, and 0.942, respectively. The themes analysis method was used to analyze the qualitative data, confirmatory factor analysis and Lisrel software were used to validate the qualitative model, and the structural equation model was used to test the hypothesis using Smart PLS software. Based on the qualitative results of the research, seven main components were identified, and a themes network was drawn. The results of the quantitative analysis have also confirmed the significance of the model's relationship between the indices, components, and dimensions. Also, the findings showed that job requirements and job resources had a positive effect on job engagement.

Keywords: job requirements, job resources, job engagement, themes analysis, structural equations

Introduction

The development is the effect of an efficient human force, and an efficient human force is a force that has a background of interests and spiritual connections with their job. Positive feedback such as job engagement can strengthen employees' intellectual and emotional connections to the organization and increase the organization's effectiveness. On the other hand, job requirements and resources, as inseparable features of every job, affect job engagement as one of the most important job feedbacks. Job resources and job requirements

are two antecedents and drivers of job engagement, whose presence or absence in the workplace can affect people's engagement to work. But to better use this effect, the specific resources and requirements of each job must first be correctly identified because the resources and demands of each job can be different depending on the nature of the job, the type of organization, and the preferences of the employees. Job requirements also include the physical, psychological, social, or organizational aspects of the job, which require a certain amount of physical or psychological effort that leads to psychological outcomes and costs (Mohseni Taklo 2021: 53). Job requirements or demands have been classified into two categories: quantitative demand and qualitative demand. Quantitative demands refer to the amount of work that a person must do in a certain time, and qualitative demands refer to the complexity of the work or the level of skills, abilities, and knowledge needed by people to do the job (Rahnama, 2016: 89). On the other hand, job resources are the physical, psychological, social or organizational characteristics of a job that help to achieve work goals and reduce job demands. Also, physical or mental costs caused by job demands are modified through job resources. In that way, they help the growth and development of the individual and at the same time reduce the pressures caused by job demands (Barabadi et al., 2015). Job demands cause the process of weakening health and job resources lead to a motivational process (Ghahramani et al., 2014). Job resources allow employees to receive positive experiences from work and improve their job performance and work attachment (Wingerden and Stoep, 2018: 235)

1. The importance and necessity of research

Currently, organizations have become an important part of the life of many people in society. Businesses are organized, and people spend many hours of their lives in these places by being employed and members of organizations. Suppose people in the organization work with engagement and interest, have attachment and belonging to their job and organization, and have enough engagement in their job field. In that case, the organization will be more successful in achieving its set goals (Mirzadarani 2013: 62) and employees will be more satisfied with their jobs.

Job engagement affects the level of attraction and strength towards work and shows the level of favorable engagement and attachment with the job. In other words, job engagement, according to Benders et al. (2017), is a state of job health that is satisfying and motivating. Based on this, enthusiastic employees have a lot of energy, are more involved in their jobs, and strongly identify with them. On the other hand, job success is a concept that is the result of a person's evaluation of his current situation and his ideals in the field of employment (Azimpour and Alilou, 2017: 7). Every organization wishes to have such

employees who do their work with engagement and thus bring profit to the organization.(Orenič,2021;84)

Despite the research showing a direct and strong relationship between the increase in the engagement of human resources and the organization's outputs, including productivity, high performance, profitability, effectiveness, efficiency, manager satisfaction, and employee satisfaction, the engagement statistics in the world are low. In Iran, the statistics of the job engagement of human resources is lower than the world average (Aghaseyed Jafari 2018: 63) and this shows the necessity of trying to improve this parameter.

Considering that the audiences of the Organization of Cinema and Audiovisual Affairs are artists and members of society's culture and art, and artists play an effective role in preserving and spreading the country's culture and art, the way the personnel of the mentioned organization interacts with the artists is very important. Therefore, according to the expectations of the managers and audience (artists) of the organization, relative to the high level of factors such as job satisfaction, internal and external motivations of employees, and improvement of the performance of the organization's employees, the factors of job requirements and job resources that are effective in the employees' job engagement will be examined. In this study, it is intended to present a model of job requirements and job resources that are effective in the employees' job engagement to provide this opportunity to the managers of the Organization of Cinema and Audiovisual Affairs of the Ministry of Culture and Islamic Guidance to use the latest human resource management solutions and new management methods in the mentioned organization. By applying the findings of this study, it can be expected that not only will the employees have a better work-life and enjoy it, but at the same time, they will have more productivity for themselves and their organizations and leading to the improvement of the performance of employees and organizations together.

Research objectives

- Designing a model of job requirements and job resources for employees' job engagement in the Organization of Cinema and Audiovisual Affairs
- Identifying the elements of job requirements and job resources of employees' job engagement in the Organization of Cinema and Audiovisual Affairs
- Validation of the job requirements and job resources model of employees' job engagement
- Effect of job requirements and job resources on employees' job engagement

Research questions

- What are the job requirements and job resources model of the employees' job engagement at the Organization of Cinema and Audiovisual Affairs?
- Which elements of job requirements and resources affect the employees' job engagement in the Organization of Cinema and Audiovisual Affairs?
- What are the global, organizing, and basic themes in the job requirements-resources model of job engagement?
- Do job requirements and job resources affect employees' job engagement?

2. Theoretical foundations

In this section, job requirements or demands, job resources, and job engagement are examined as the main components of the research. Then a brief introduction of the theories and models available in this field is examined.

Job requirements, job resources, and job engagement

Along with the existing conceptual and content definitions for the variables mentioned for the research, the theoretical and research foundations of the relationship between these variables will clarify the limits and scope of the research problem. One of the proposed theories to explain the variables of this study is the theory of the Job Demands-Resources model (JD-R). The first basic assumption is that when people's workplaces are different, the characteristics of the workplace can be divided into two classes, job demands and job resources. The second basic assumption in the JD-R model is the relationship between job demands and resources with health and attitudinal outcomes. Based on the second assumption, this model assumes that job demands (burdensomeness, role ambiguity, and role conflict) are likely to lead to different reactions (psychological stress, decreased health). In contrast, it leads to feelings of disappointment or failure. Such feelings cause isolation behavior and negative attitudes towards work, such as a decrease in organizational commitment, job attachment, job engagement, and an increase in the desire to leave the service (Damerouti et al., 2001: 86).

Job requirements are stimuli imposed on a person by other people or from the physical workplace and require attention and response. In general, job requirements refer to the physical, psychological, social, or organizational characteristics of a job that requires physical or mental effort from the employee and therefore are related to some physiological and mental costs (Mohagheghi, 2014: 67). Job requirements are things that must be done. They are not necessarily negative as long as they do not exceed the individual's ability to comply with them. Some people may experience job stress when faced with tasks that require more effort.

Therefore, they face many costs that call these stresses and negative responses such as depression, anxiety, or burnout. Work pressure, unfavorable physical conditions of the workplace, emotional requirements due to interaction with customers, and issues related to job security, organizational changes, and workload are part of job requirements (Schaufeli, 2017: 71).

Job resources can affect important outcomes in the workplace by affecting job engagement. Also, these resources can affect two important outcomes in the workplace, including job performance and intention to leave the job, through the creation of job attitudes and positive moods such as job engagement (based on the job engagement model of Bakker and Demerouti, 2005). Job resources affect organizational outcomes by influencing job engagement. (Karimi and Mardani, 2020; 7). Job resources include individual resources and organizational resources. Individual resources are characteristics generally related to flexibility and refer to a person's feelings based on his ability to control and successfully influence the environment (Hobfoll, 2002: Zargaran Moghadam, 2012).

Many definitions have been proposed regarding job engagement, but a definition accepted and approved by everyone has not yet been presented in this field. McLeod and Clarke (2009) state the reason for this lack of unity by saying that employees' job engagement is one of the new paradigms in the field of human resources and has multiple definitions due to the various ways of using it. Most definitions acknowledge that engagement originates from personal and environmental resources (Macey and Schneider, 2009). He presented the first official definition of the employees' engagement to the theme that employees identify themselves with the performance of their roles and bring them under control. He states that in engagement, people show and use their physical, cognitive, and emotional powers to fulfill their role.

Employees are the key component of any organization and enthusiastic employees are considered its most important asset (Padhi and Panda 2015;79).An enthusiastic employee considers his thoughts and emotions as belonging to the organization, has a romantic feeling for his goals, and as a result, is committed to his values. Organizations that benefit from enthusiastic employees; They have more well-being, productivity and satisfaction, less stress and burnout. (Damghanian et al. 2019 ;2)

Job engagement as feedback is an important variable that helps increase the organization's effectiveness. The higher the level of employees' job engagement in an organization, the more effective they will be (Zargaran Moghadam, 2012). Job engagement has been defined as a positive and satisfying state of mind in the field of work, which is characterized by three components of professional energy, professional dedication (commitment), and professional fascination (attraction). Professional energy is characterized

by a high level of energy, mental flexibility at work, and a willingness to try and resist problems. Professional dedication is characterized by a sense of importance, engagement, desire, pride, and challenge at work. The third dimension of job engagement is professional fascination, characterized by full concentration and immersion in work so that time passes quickly while working. It is difficult for a person to be separated from his work (Schaufeli, 2017: 71). Professional energy and dedication are opposite poles of fatigue and negative attitude to work and depersonalization in job burnout, respectively (Smith, 2018).

Job engagement theories

Various theories have been proposed about job engagement, among which the following theories can be mentioned:

1. Social exchange theory: According to social exchange theory, relationships between employees and employers are based on mutual norms. In cases where employees feel that they are performing well and are being evaluated by the employer, it is likely that they will show higher engagement levels.
2. Conservation of resources theory: This theory is a motivational theory that explains a major part of human behavior based on the evolutionary need to obtain and preserve resources for survival based on human nature. Hobfoll's conservation of resources theory begins with the principle that people strive to acquire, maintain, nurture, and protect the things which they mainly value. Conservation of resources theory follows the understanding that cognitions are strongly biased toward increasing resources and decreasing resource loss.
3. The broaden-and-build theory (theory of positive emotions): The mentioned theory, which is in the field of positive emotions, was presented for the first time by Barbara Frederickson. This theory says that positive emotions have evolved to increase people's psychological adaptation and help human survival. The broaden-and-build theory argues that engagement is more likely to occur when people experience positive rather than negative emotions, creating a broad space for a set of intellectual activities. The active, positive effect is important for stimulation (Mohagheghi, 2014: 67).

Models of job requirements, job resources, and job engagement

There are various models about job requirements, job resources, and job engagement, including Rich et al., Schaufeli et al. (2008), Arnik's Institute's job engagement model, Koock's engagement stimulants model (2008), Miao's satisfaction, motivation and engagement model (2012), psychology of appreciation of colleagues (Siteforce), Labor Studies Institute's engagement model, Robinson et al.'s engagement model (2004), miao (2012), the psychology

of appreciation of colleagues (Site Force), the engagement model of the Institute of Work Studies, the motivational model of employees, Robinson et al.'s engagement stimulants of the employees(2004).Mohagheghan Panah's hierarchy of engagement (2007), Costa et al.'s work engagement network (2015), Rana et al.'s proposed theoretical model of employee engagement (2014), Bakker and Demerotti's JD-R model (2007). Zanta Polo et al.'s job resource demands model (2008), Bakker and Demerotti's job resource requirements model (2008), Hackman et al.'s job characteristics model (2005) and so on.

Experimental background

Various categories of job requirements, job resources, and job engagement can be seen in previous studies and research. Based on this, to explain the empirical background, a summary of the studies related to the model of job requirements and job resources affecting the employees' job engagement has been classified and included in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of the research done concerning the present study

Findings	Goals	Researchers
The research sample was 200 employees of the Iraqi Ministry of Water. The result of the research was the positive and significant effect of job resources on organizational commitment and the negative and significant effect of job resources on job burnout.	The effect of job demands and job resources on individual performance with the mediating role of job burnout and organizational commitment	Ria Eidan Mosybed al-Jasmas (2017)
The research sample was 125 employees of Mobarakeh Steel Company in Isfahan. The results of structural modeling confirmed the effect of job resources on job engagement and the relationship between job resources and demands.	The effect of job resources and job demands on job burnout and job engagement of the employees based on the JDR model	Sedigheh Zargaran Moghadam (2012)
The research sample was 340 employees of Razavi Khorasan Province industries. The obtained data fit the theoretical model of the research and confirm it, and the job resources, directly and indirectly, affect job engagement through psychological capital.	Formulation of the job engagement model according to job resources, job requirements, and psychological capital	Hassan Mohagheghi (2014)
The research sample was 1698 employees in four different work groups. This study showed that different interventions are needed to	The relationship between job demands, job resources	Schaufeli and Bakker (2004)

reduce job burnout and increase job engagement.	with job burnout, and job engagement	
The findings show that while organizational interaction positively affects an individual's ability to adapt to changes, job duties have a different effect and uncover potential obstacles to managing change in the organization.	Engagement of employees, positive organizational culture, and individual adaptability:	Prant and Lowlice (2018)
The findings show that all three types of organizational pessimism (i.e., perceptual pessimism, emotional pessimism, and behavioral pessimism) have a negative relationship with employee performance, while employee engagement modifies this relationship.	Organizational pessimism and employee performance: The modifying role of employee engagement	Arsalan (2018)

Based on the review of theoretical foundations and research background, it can be said that many organizations believe that their greatest capital is human power. But it must be accepted that a force is a real capital that is enthusiastic and interested in its work with all its heart and uses all its abilities to perform its duties correctly and fully, in line with the organization's goals. Employees with high job engagement have a correct understanding of the organization's vision and duties, and they accompany and help their managers with follow-up and perseverance. It is possible to imagine that an organization with many enthusiastic and motivated personnel has a happy and dynamic workplace and can achieve its operational goals with greater speed and less cost. International research has proven that, under equal conditions, doubling the level of engagement of the personnel is equivalent to doubling the organization's profitability.

Increasing organizational engagement has significant effects on positive parameters of human resources such as job satisfaction, increased work motivation, mental health in the workplace, reduced stress, and more happiness. At the same time, it leads to the improvement of the efficiency factors of an organization.

A careful examination of these researches and suggestions shows no unique and specific plan to increase people's engagement. Many activities can lead to the improvement of this vital parameter of the organization. Different organizations have prepared and implemented different plans to improve the engagement of their employees. Meanwhile, job requirements and resources can be the best definition and improvement plan for creating a

culture of engagement in organizations. Therefore, this study examines the model of job requirements and resources that are effective in the employees' job engagement.

3. Methodology

The research method is a mixed exploratory (qualitative and quantitative) which is explained as follows:

In this study, the main factors, components, and dimensions of job requirements and job resources were extracted using the qualitative method of themes analysis as well as semi-structured interviews with experts on the topic, and then using questionnaires whose items were obtained from the analysis of the theme and approved by the panel of academic experts and administrative system experts, the model of job requirements and job resources of employees' job engagement was examined with the designed factorial model and the use of various statistical techniques, Cronbach's alpha, Smart PLS, and SPSS.

The qualitative part of the research with Braun and Clark's themes analysis strategy (Brown and Clark, 2006) and their six-stage guide (including getting to know the data, producing primary codes, searching for themes, examining themes, defining themes, and final writing and analyzing) has been done with the aim of understanding and extracting inherent meanings from employees' experiences, around the issue of job requirements and job resources that affect employees' job engagement. The statistical population was 200 employees of the Organization of Cinema and Audiovisual Affairs in Iran. In the first stage of the research, to identify the components of job requirements and job resources that affect engagement, 17 interviews were conducted with human resource experts (including experts and managers of the Organization of Cinema and Audiovisual Affairs) who were selected by purposive sampling. The interview texts were directly implemented, and themes analysis was used to extract themes.

In the quantitative part of the research, three questionnaires were used as necessary. The first researcher-made questionnaire is related to obtaining experts' opinions about the importance of the items (the items were obtained from expert interviews, and the findings from the interviews with experts were drawn in the themes network), and each of the factors was scored from one to seven separately. The second researcher-made questionnaire examines the current situation of the Organization of Cinema and Audiovisual Affairs regarding the items (research findings) that were extracted as basic codes during the interview stage. Their effect on job engagement (Utrecht model used) was discussed in the seven spectra from one to seven, and in the third questionnaire, because in the research model, Schaufeli and Bakker job engagement model was used and for coordination of Schaufeli components (professional energy, professional dedication, and professional fascination) with the standard Utrecht

engagement questionnaire, therefore, the Utrecht questionnaire was used. The items of the model of job requirements and job resources of the researcher were examined and tested with Utrecht's standard questionnaire of job engagement.

The questionnaire on the importance of the items was analyzed by the method of confirmatory factor analysis and Lisrel software, and the questionnaire on the current situation of job requirements and job resources and the questionnaire on job engagement were analyzed by the variance-based structural equation model and Smart PLS software.

The content validity of the questionnaire was confirmed by several scientific and administrative, and organizational experts. In order to ensure the validity of the items, confirmatory factor analysis was first used. Cronbach's alpha method was used to measure and evaluate the reliability of the research tools.

4. Findings

The findings are in two parts, qualitative and quantitative, which are presented as follows:

The findings of the qualitative part: After interviewing the experts and ensuring the saturation point, and analyzing the content of the results of the interviews, a global theme, seven organizing components (themes), and 64 basic themes have been extracted, which are shown in Table 2:

Table 2: The main and sub-components of the research

Global themes	Organizing themes	Basic themes
Job Requirements	Quantitative job challenges(QC)	Strictness at work(Q ₁) Physical fatigue (Q ₂) Ambiguity of role(Q ₃) Role conflict(Q ₄) Congestion and time pressure to do the work(Q ₅) The high volume of work in the organization(Q ₆) Numerous and cumbersome rules and regulations(Q ₇) Ambiguous and incomprehensible tasks(Q ₈) The requirement for strict adherence to hierarchy(Q ₉) Intense and complicated bureaucracy(Q ₁₀)
	Qualitative job challenges(QCH)	Work-life balance(Q ₁₁) Client requirements and pressures(Q ₁₂) Job excitement(Q ₁₃) Fatigue due to work pressures(Q ₁₄) Organizational changes(Q ₁₅) Job stress(Q ₁₆) Job burnout(Q ₁₇) Being threatened by supervisors(Q ₁₈) The sensitivity of work(Q ₁₉) Fear of managers and colleagues(Q ₂₀)
Job Resources	Organizational support (OS)	Job security(S ₁) Management and administrative support(S ₂) Organizational participation(S ₃)
	Opportunities for growth and promotion (OU)	Training and development of managers and employees(S ₄) Job progress path(S ₅) Equal job opportunities(S ₆) Being seen at work(S ₇) The possibility of employee growth and excellence(S ₈) Performance evaluation(S ₉) Organizational learning(S ₁₀) Finding talent in appointments (S ₁₁) Meritocracy an appointment(S ₁₂)

	Social and interpersonal responsibilities of the employees(S1R)	<p>Support of colleagues and supervisors(S13)</p> <p>Respect each other(S14)</p> <p>Appreciation(S15)</p> <p>Empathy with colleagues(S16)</p> <p>Fairness in decision making(S17)</p> <p>Friendship(S18)</p> <p>The atmosphere of the group(S19)</p> <p>Dedication to work(S20)</p> <p>Workplace(S21)</p> <p>Justice in decision making(S22)</p> <p>Emotional support(S23)</p> <p>Social support(S24)</p> <p>Instrumental support (providing instruments needed for work) (S25)</p> <p>Information support (providing the information needed to do the job) (S26)</p> <p>Education(S27)</p> <p>To be understood(S28)</p>
	Administrative and financial incentives(AFI)	<p>Workload-based rewards(S29)</p> <p>Contingent incentives(S30)</p> <p>Salary(S31)</p> <p>Amenities(S32)</p> <p>Job Benefits(S33)</p> <p>Performance-based rewards(S34)</p>
	Job characteristics and elements (JFE)	<p>Diversity in tasks and skills(S35)</p> <p>Performance feedback(S36)</p> <p>Job enrichment(S37)</p> <p>Significant work(S38)</p> <p>Job rotation(S39)</p> <p>The importance of having a job(S40)</p> <p>Autonomy at work(S41)</p> <p>Independence at work(S42)</p> <p>Role transparency(S43)</p> <p>Job development(S44)</p>

The themes analysis method was used to identify job requirements factors and resources affecting job requirements and draw a conceptual model in the themes network. In the research background stage, the statistical population included the research in books, articles, sources, and electronic data included in the information sources. In the interview stage, the statistical population was the Organization of Cinema and Audiovisual Affairs experts. In this stage, sampling continued until theoretical saturation was obtained (17 interviews). A saturation point is a point in research where all concepts are well-defined and explained. The library studies tools were used to familiarize with the literature and background of the research, and semi-structured interviews were used to survey the experts about the job requirements and job resources affecting the employee's engagement in the Organization of Cinema and Audiovisual Affairs. Table 3 shows the main themes of the model of job requirements and job resources of Organization of Cinema and Audiovisual Affairs employees in the form of a themes network.

Table 3: The themes network of job requirement-job resources of employees' job engagement of Organization of Cinema and Audiovisual Affairs

The findings of the quantitative part: To check the validity of the model obtained from the qualitative part, the confirmatory factor analysis method and Lisrel software were used. The statistical population was the Organization of Cinema and Audiovisual Affairs employees, and 127 people were selected as a sample according to Morgan's table. Among the 127 participants, all questionnaires were included in the analysis. In order to collect data, a researcher-made questionnaire was used. This questionnaire included 64 items with a seven-point Likert scale in order to check the validity of the initial conceptual model. To ensure the validity and reliability of the questionnaire, after searching and studying various specialized books and articles, administrative and academic experts were consulted, and their opinions were used.

The factor loading was estimated for each of the factors or components based on the conceptual model to measure and evaluate the reliability of the questionnaire items. After entering the data on the importance of items questionnaire (127 questionnaires) using confirmatory factor analysis, the general structure of the research questionnaires was validated. For the confirmatory factor analysis, the standard factor loading was calculated. The confirmatory factor analysis of the questionnaire of job requirements and job resources is presented in Charts 1 and 2. The standard factor loading of confirmatory factor analysis to measure the strength of the relationship between each factor (latent variable) and its visible variables (questionnaire items) was obtained in all cases greater than 0.4. Therefore, the factor structure of the questionnaire of job requirements and job resources can be confirmed.

Chi-Square=469.96, df=169, P-value=0.06790, RMSEA=0.043

Chart 1: Standard factor loading of confirmatory factor analysis of job requirements questionnaire

Chart 2: Standard factor loading of confirmatory factoranalysis of job resources questionnaire

After calculating the standard factor loading, a significance test was performed. To check the significance of the relationship between the variables, the t-value was used.

Based on the results observed in charts 3 and 4, the factor loading of the t-value of each of the dimensions of the job requirements questionnaire at the 5% confidence level is greater than 1.96. Therefore, the significance of the relationship between the model's indices, components, and dimensions has been confirmed.

Chi-Square=469.96, df=169, P-value=0.06790, RMSEA=0.043

Chart 3: T-value of confirmatory factor analysis of job requirements questionnaire

Chi-Square=2216.21, df=892, P-value=0.09540, RMSEA=0.021

Chart 4: T-value of confirmatory factor analysis of job resources questionnaire

According to Tables 4 and 5, the fitting goodness indices of job requirements and job resources questionnaire, the model has a good fit.

Table 4: Goodness fitting indices of job requirements questionnaire

(NNFI)	(NFI)	(AFI)	(GFI)	(RMSEA)	(X2/pdf)	Fitting indices
>0/9	>0/9	>0/9	>0/9	<0/05	1-3	Acceptable values
0.92	0.97	0.94	0.96	2/78	0.043	Calculated values

Table 5: Goodness fitting indices of job resource questionnaire

(NNFI)	(NFI)	(AFI)	(GFI)	(RMSEA)	(X2/pdf)	Fitting indices
>0/9	>0/9	>0/9	>0/9	<0/05	1-3	Acceptable values
0.94	0.92	0.98	0.99	2/48	0.021	Calculated values

Based on the observed results and according to the appropriate fit of the model, we can rely on the research findings, and the presented model is approved.

In order to test the research hypothesis (job requirements and job resources have a significant effect on job engagement), the variance-based structural equation model was used. The variance-based structural equation model is a comprehensive statistical approach for testing hypotheses about the relationships between observed and latent variables.

In order to study the effect of job requirements and job resources on job engagement, the final model was obtained by Smart_PLS-3-2-9 software, as shown in chart. 5.

Chart 5: The final model for the effect of job requirements and job resources on job engagement through regression coefficients

Chart 6: Significance of the effect of job requirements and job resources on job engagement through p-value

Table 6: Estimation of the regression coefficients of the main hypothesis model of the research

Result	T-value	Significance level	R ²	Effect coefficient	Main hypothesis
Confirmed	3/221	0/031	0/301	0/271*	Job engagement ← Job Requirements
Confirmed	4/645	0/021	0/301	0/309*	Job engagement ← Job Resources

The effect coefficients estimated in Table 6 show whether each component is effective or not. As can be seen in the table, considering that the p-value of the effect of job requirements and job resources on job engagement was less than 0.05, the effect coefficients of 0.271 and 0.309 are significant at the 95% confidence level, and the effect of job requirements and job resources on job engagement was confirmed.

The basic question raised is whether this model is good. To answer this question, average variance extracted statistics, composite reliability (CR), and Cronbach's alpha was examined for the model fit's goodness. According to the output of PLS and the results of Tables

6 to 7 obtained from the output of SmartPLS software, it can be concluded that the mentioned model is good in terms of fit indices.

Table 7: The convergent validity index for the goodness of the research model

Results	Indices value in the model	Standard value	Variable name
The model fitting is good.	0/896	0.5 or higher	Job engagement
The model fitting is good.	0/812	0.5 or higher	Job Requirements
The model fitting is good.	0/783	0.5 or higher	Job Resources

Chart 7: Studying and comparing average variance extracted (AVE) index with 0.5

Another factor in evaluating the internal consistency reliability of the model is Cronbach's alpha. The value of this coefficient varies from 0 to 1, values higher than 0.7 are accepted, and values less than 0.6 are considered unfavorable .

Table 8: Cronbach's alpha index

Results	Indices value in the model	Standard value	Variable name
The model fitting is good.	0/942	0.7 or higher	Job engagement
The model fitting is good.	0/768	0.7 or higher	Job Requirements
The model fitting is good.	0/930	0.7 or higher	Job Resources

Chart 8: Studying and comparing Cronbach's alpha index with 0.7

Here, the evaluation of the general part of the model, which includes the measurement and the structural part, is discussed simultaneously. For this purpose, the Goodness of Fit (GOF) standard, which is related to the general part of structural equation models, was used. Wetzels et al. (2009) introduced three values of 0.01, 0.25, and 0.36 as weak, moderate, and strong for GOF. This means that if the value of 0.01 and close to it is calculated as GOF in a model, it can be concluded that the overall fit of that model is weak, and the relationships between the model structures should be corrected. In the same way, this is maintained for the other two values of GOF (0.25 moderate overall fit and 0.36 strong overall fit) (Davari and Rezazadeh, 2019).

$$GOF = \sqrt{\text{Communalities} \times R^2}$$

Average communalities are obtained from the average communal values of the latent variables of the first order of the model, i.e., job engagement, job requirements, and job resources of employees. The communalities values and R2 are listed in Table 9.

Table 9: The communalities and R2 values of research variables

R2 value	Communalities (Q2) value	Latent variables of the model
0/301	0/678	Job engagement
	0/349	Job Requirements
	0/614	Job Resources

$$GOF = \sqrt{0.547 \times 0.301} = 0.405$$

According to the three values of 0.01, 0.25, and 0.36 as weak, moderate, and strong values for GOF, the result of 0.405 for GOF shows the overall good fit of the model.

According to the steps carried out in this research, by reviewing the main questions of the research; And also focusing on the objectives of the present research, it is clear that in this research, after examining the theoretical foundations and literature of the subject in the field of job requirements and job resources and engagement using the theme analysis method, 220 codes, 64 basic themes and 7 organizing themes And an overarching theme was identified, and based on this, the theme network model was designed, then the validity of the model was checked with confirmatory factor analysis, and in the next step, the hypothesis test was checked based on the model. The results of the quantitative analysis have also confirmed the significance of the relationship between the indicators, components and dimensions of the model. Also, the findings showed that job requirements and job resources had a positive effect on job engagement.

Conclusion

The present study aimed to provide a model of job requirements and job resources affecting employees' job engagement. The results of the research showed that job requirements and job resources have a significant effect on the job engagement of employees. Also, by extracting the components and elements of the job requirements and job resources, the job requirements-job resources theme model of job engagement was developed. The findings of this study can provide managers with useful insight to reduce the elements of job requirements (such as role ambiguity, strictness at work, numerous and cumbersome rules and regulations, the requirement of strict adherence to hierarchy, intense and complicated bureaucracy, etc.) and also, strengthening job resources (such as job security, management, and administrative support, training and development of managers and employees, finding talent in appointments, informational, instrumental and social support, etc.) which plays a very important role in the employees' job engagement.

The findings of this study were consistent with the findings of Anita (2014), Smith and Beatitci (2015), Prent and Lovelace (2018), Kerry Kanermol (2018), Ahuja and Chanoverdi (2017), Miao (2016), Rao (2017), Rahnama (2014), Halo (2013), Zargaran Moghadam (2012), Adibi (2011), Bakker and Demerouti (2008), Mohagheghi (2014), Vermuten et al. (2019), Akgendoz et al. (2019), Wingerden and Steop (2018). Bakker and Demerouti's studies have the most consistent with the present study. However, in that study, the statistical population was selected in the industry sector, which has an obvious difference from the statistical population of the present study, which is the employees of the cultural sector (artists), in terms of the type of activity and the type of audience. In terms of dealing with the subject of the job

requirements -the job resources model that is affecting the job engagement of employees in a government complex, also from a cultural point of view (which is one of the strengths and important innovations of this study), this subject has not been addressed in any of the previous studies. It is the first time that research has been done concerning this issue.

The framework provided in this study is different from the components of the models presented in the 2000s until now. With a deep theoretical study and testing of the collected data, it has taken a complementary approach and tried to add more depth and richness to the previous research by extracting the components from the interviews conducted with the experts and matching them with the real environment of the studied organizations. The results of related research until 2020 show that job requirements and job resources that affect job engagement include variables such as work volume, job satisfaction, commitment, workload, role ambiguity, job uncertainty, and physical workplace (Miao, 2016; 83), health issues and energy wastage of employees, job control, supervisor support, access to information and good organizational atmosphere, social support (Boland et al., 2017: 42), independence, performance feedback and professional development opportunities, feedback, autonomy, time pressure, shift work, conflict requirements, shift work pressure, excess workload (Allameh et al., 2014), but in this study, the factors of social and interpersonal responsibilities, job characteristics and elements, as well as administrative and financial incentives were also prioritized. Another difference between this study and other related research is the type of research method. Previous researches were generally qualitative or quantitative, but in conducting this study, a mixed research method was used.

This study has tried to present the components of job requirements and job resources in line with the job engagement of the Organization of Cinema and Audiovisual Affairs employees. Job demands are among the factors that increase the level of stress of people in the workplace. In addition to job demands, people have many resources such as skills, support from colleagues and technology, etc., as many job resources in the workplace so that they can meet the many demands that are made of them in their jobs.

When people's job demands are at a high level and job resources are at a low level, they decrease job engagement in such a way that job resources indirectly decrease job engagement by reducing the demands caused by psychological job pressure (Schaufeli and Bakker, 2004: 293). Therefore, by creating solutions in the workplace, it is possible to reduce the psychological pressure caused by high job demands.

This study shows that resources and requirements such as quantitative job challenges, qualitative job challenges, administrative and financial incentives, job characteristics and elements, social and interpersonal responsibilities, organizational support, and opportunities for growth and promotion affect the job engagement of employees of the Organization of

Cinema and Audiovisual Affairs Human resource managers in the Organization of Cinema and Audiovisual Affairs can help their employees by designing job and administrative interventions related to reducing the quantitative and qualitative job requirements and strengthening job resources such as organizational support, opportunities for growth and promotion, clarifying job characteristics, etc. until by overcoming job stress in a stressful workplace, increase their job engagement and have better job performance.

The results of this study's qualitative research (first phase) have shown that the effective factors in job engagement in terms of job requirements and job resources consist of 7 main components and 64 sub-components. The results of the quantitative part (second phase) show that the items of each sub-factor had a significant number and an acceptable standard coefficient, which indicates the high validity of these factors. The results of factor analysis have shown that each component's factors have a high correlation with the main component. Seven components also had a significant and positive relationship with each other. Therefore, it can be concluded that the researcher has been successful in reaching the research goal and answering the research questions and this research has been successfully completed.

The results of this study from a theoretical aspect for experts and scholars of human resources management and especially for executive managers, and from a practical point of view, it is important to select, train, and maintain the human resources needed by all public and private organizations, especially the Organization of Cinema and Audiovisual Affairs.

Based on the results of this study and considering that the complicated bureaucracy and work-life balance in the confirmatory factor analysis have the strongest index for measuring the variable of job requirements- quantitative and qualitative job challenges, as well as job security, training and development of managers and employees, informational support and performance-based rewards have the strongest indices for measuring job resource variables- organizational support, opportunities for growth and promotion, social and interpersonal responsibilities, and administrative and financial incentives; therefore, it is suggested:

1. The administrative hierarchy should be reduced, facilitating the work processes.
2. Dealing with work and family are two important aspects of every person's life, so managers should consider the following support programs: counseling services for employees, time management training, stress management training, and flexible work programs such as telecommuting.
3. Managers should consider cases such as appreciation, a happy workplace, effective communication, an increase in work quality standards, honesty, recognition of employees' interests, and clarifying the organization's goals to create security for employees.

4. Training empowers existing human resources (Saidipour, Mohammadipour, 2020: 55) and guarantees future success. Therefore, managers should pay attention to these things in training programs, including focusing on the needs of employees, matching educational content with organizational goals, focusing on educational feedback, accompanying employees during the training course, focusing on practical training instead of theoretical training, and analyzing and optimizing training programs.
5. The information needed to do the work should be provided to the employees completely and transparently and away from bias.
6. Managers should keep the following things in mind when awarding rewards to employees: fairness and justice in awarding rewards, not having a large gap between the rewards of managers and employees, a sense of equality in receiving rewards, objective and transparent rewards, frequency and repetition in awarding rewards, flexibility, and the existence of contingent rewards.
7. Job duties should also be stated in such a way that for employees, the work is clear from beginning to end, they have a complete and clear view of their job duties, and employees can see the effect of their performance in the organization.

In addition to the lack of domestic research background on the research subject as one of the present study's limitations, the research has only discussed the components due to time and practical limitations. The statistical population of the research included the employees of the Organization of Cinema and Audiovisual Affairs; therefore, considering the possible differences between the cultural organizations and other organizations, these results should be more carefully considered and generalized in other organizations. Other researchers can examine factors that affect employees' job engagement, such as personal and environmental factors. In addition, since the results of this study were obtained on a limited scale and only in the public sector with a cultural approach, a more comprehensive study and comparison of job requirements and job resources of employees' job engagement in different organizations may bring different results, in this regard, researchers are advised to pay attention to these concepts in future research.

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